

Cross-Cultural Construction of Latin American Literary Identity in a Norwegian Academic Context

“FORTVILELESENS MUSIKK (Jorge Luis Borges, 1899–1986)”

ENGLISH TRANSLATION

The Music of Despair

Jorge Luis Borges (1899–1986)

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Borges, who was an expert on Old Norse literature, translated many of the sagas into Spanish. Of all the Scandinavian countries, it was actually Norway that he preferred. He admired the Norwegian people's honesty and innocence, as well as their relationship with nature. Although Borges was born in Buenos Aires and was of aristocratic descent, the mixture of blood in his veins is typical of most Argentines: criollo (a mix of Spanish and Indigenous blood) and European (his grandmother was English).

He received his education in Switzerland. It was during this period that he began to write—first as a translator and literary critic, and later as an author.

After the Second World War, he returned home to his family. During this period, Borges lived a life among the intellectuals in Buenos Aires. For economic reasons, he was forced to give lectures to university students, something that caused his character—his life and his thoughts—to become well known. He assumed the role of an "enfant terrible" who took pleasure in shocking his conventional listeners.

Over time, he became internationally recognized and was appointed Doctor Honoris Causa at many universities. He was also awarded a number of prizes; the "Premio Cervantes," which is awarded to Spanish-speaking writers, to name but one. He was nominated for the Nobel Prize in

Literature several times, but he never received it. "Because of his political views," some of his readers claim.

Paradoxically, he went blind at the exact time he was appointed Director of the National Library. Nevertheless, he continued his literary work.

The environment he frequented wilded his imagination to write about the heroes of the war of independence against Spain (some of them were relatives) and about the brave courage linked to "malevos" (men from poor neighborhoods who lived on the outskirts of Buenos Aires at the beginning of this century).

It has been said that a mirror hanging in his parents' bedroom influenced him to reflect on mirrors, the infinite, and labyrinths. The truth is that he generally transformed life experiences and impressions into masterpieces. A clear example of this is an accident he suffered that made him seriously ill. He suffered from high fever and hallucinations. From this came an analysis of time, dreams, and death in the things he wrote.

Love is an area Borges concerned himself with a great deal. But when he depicts love, he often does so from a puritanical perspective. Paradoxically, sexuality is mentioned as part of love in a story about an encounter with a Norwegian girl...

It is worth noting his private life: he married his first love after she became a widow from her first marriage. They separated after a short time. Later in life, fate brought him together with a young literary student (with whom he had his own strange relationship) and they traveled the world together. She became his wife—Articulo Mortis [at the point of death]—in Switzerland, and with his inheritance, they established a foundation for the promotion of art in her name. Her name is Maria Kodama. It is in Switzerland that Borges died. He declared, as he left Argentina, that "Buenos Aires no longer exists." A statement which, like many of his other remarks, provoked scandal and caused fury among many. In a way, it was true for him that Buenos Aires—with its malevos—no longer existed.

Among his many books, we could mention "Aleph", "Fictions", "Fervour of Buenos Aires", etc.; most of what he wrote has been translated into several languages.

In addition to his deep sensitivity, sparkling intelligence, moral courage, and unusual talent, Borges was, in my opinion, a man who was faithful to himself and, above all, "loyal to the truth." He spoke about himself with the most striking modesty, about his work with ironic contempt, and about his success and fame with sadness over having devoted his whole life and all his energy to the act of writing and not to being happy...